

Analyzing Repetitive DNA Involved in Tissue Regeneration in Echinoderms

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Abstract

Past studies have shown that echinoderms can undergo whole-body regeneration (WBR) when exposed to trauma. Among echinoderms, *Sclerodactyla briareus* (a sea cucumber) and *Ophioderma brevispina* (a brittle star) have shown great regenerative potential. Nevertheless, the specific biological mechanisms for WBR are currently unknown. Our team sequenced genetic data from this species of brittle star and sea cucumber to start building the framework necessary for these organisms to become models in tissue regeneration. However, the currently available *de novo* assemblies of PacBio and Illumina genomes of the brittle star and the sea cucumber are fragmented. We can partly explain the degree of fragmentation of these assemblies by the frequency of repetitive DNA elements in comparison with other better-understood genomes, such as of *Asterias rubens* (a common starfish). Interestingly, at the same time that repetitive DNA can hamper the *de novo* genome assemblies of the brittle star and the sea cucumber, they could affect the gene regulatory mechanisms involved in WBR. Comparative genomics may allow us to test the relation between tissue regeneration and different repetitive elements in the echinoderm genome. However, we lack a consistent repeat classification system that includes all types of repetitive DNA. We also lack the tools to enumerate the number of different repeats assembled using *de novo* strategies such as REP*denovo*. Therefore, we leverage on the chromosome level assembly of the common starfish to propose an improved classification system of repetitive DNA elements and apply it to the genome analysis of the brittle star and the sea cucumber. We also proposed new methodologies that are promising in quantifying repeats in *de novo* assemblies using the genome of the common starfish.

Keywords: bioinformatics; Echinodermata; hairy sea cucumber; regrowth; sea stars; serpent star.

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Introduction

Humans have limited regenerative properties. However, certain animals that are related to humans have shown widespread regenerative potential, such as the echinoderms. Echinoderms can undergo complete organ regeneration when exposed to trauma [6, 8, 17]. As seen in Figure 1, the relationship between echinoderms and humans exists through a common deuterostome ancestor [8]. However, throughout evolution, the regenerative abilities of the echinoderms have remained intact while those of humans have rapidly decreased.

Figure 1: Evolutionary relationship between Echinoderms and Chordates and their respective regenerative potential. Figure by Dr. Vladimir Mashanov.

Past studies have yet to explain the specific biological mechanisms for echinoderms' extensive tissue regeneration. A novel finding from available echinoderm genomes is their large number of repetitive elements [5]. These repetitive sequences range from dozens of nucleotides to several thousand base pairs. It is known that repetitive sequences comprise much of the heterochromatin in eukaryotes [21, 9]. Heterochromatin refers to a state of dense DNA packaging that keeps the genetic information unavailable from transcriptional machinery [9]. As such, repetitive sequences likely play an integral role in chromosomal stability and gene silencing, shedding light on how these sequences may influence differential gene expression in eukaryotic organisms such as the echinoderms [21].

Gene annotation is an important task to categorize the various types of repetitive sequences and discern their role in the differential gene expression involved in the regeneration of echinoderm tissues [13]. Gene annotation allows for the achievement of these goals by efficiently naming and elucidating the structure of a specific gene sequence of interest. This process is conceptually distinct from gene prediction which is a process that involves discovering the length of a gene from point "x" to point "y." Past research that has utilized

gene annotation methods have already implicated numerous repetitive sequences in tandem that code for secretory and fibrinogen-related proteins during organ regrowth in echinoderms [33]. Many long terminal repeat (LTR) retroelements and transposable elements have also been found to be differentially expressed during the regeneration of echinoderm tissues. Specifically, researchers have discovered that the most up-regulated element, a transposon, demonstrated a dramatic increase in its expression in the area around the wound, returning to normal levels only after regeneration had completed [17]. These studies, along with others in the field, provide evidence that repetitive sequences in the genomes of echinoderms allow for differential gene expression that may play a role in the regenerative properties observed in these organisms. As such, the high proportion of repetitive elements in the genomes of echinoderms is likely to positively influence the gene regulatory mechanisms involved in complete tissue regeneration [16]. Therefore, qualifying and quantifying these repeats are key to understanding their role in the up- or down-regulation of genes associated with tissue regeneration.

The common European starfish, *Asterias rubens* Linnaeus, 1758, is an echinoderm species whose annotated genome is of high quality with a reduced degree of fragmentation [30, 28, 20].

Figure 2: *Asterias rubens*, otherwise known as the common starfish. In the foreground, another individual starfish is undergoing regeneration [4].

Because of this, the qualification and quantification of the repetitive elements present can be more easily accomplished. By studying the repetitive sequence content of *A. rubens*, additional studies on non-model organisms may be possible through repeat masking. Two non-model echinoderm species, *Sclerodactyla briareus* Lesueur, 1824 (hairy sea cucumber) and *Ophioderma brevispinum* Say, 1825 (brittle star), for example, have been shown in past studies to have great regenerative potential [1, 18].

Figure 3: *Sclerodactyla briareus*, commonly known as the hairy sea cucumber [10].

Figure 4: *Ophioderma brevispinum*, commonly known as the brittle star [11].

With the high-confidence compilation of a reference genome from *A. rubens*, the annotation and the qualification and quantification of repeats of *S. briareus* and *O. brevispinum* genomes may be possible.

During our research on *A. rubens*, we encountered disparities throughout published literature dealing with the classification of the various types of repetitive genomic elements. We devised a novel classification system to more efficiently and accurately compare repetitive elements. The classification system aims to detach the biological meaning of a group of repeats from its hierarchical level and organize them into a comparable hierarchical structure. This structure closely aligns with current biological classification systems to maintain continuity and clarity. Ultimately, the system provides more accurate information when looking at evolutionary relationships and functions of repetitive genomic repeats.

Our original hypothesis stated that we could estimate the abundance of repetitive elements in the *de novo* assembly of echinoderm genomes on the basis of their coverage in comparison to the coverage of single-copy orthologous genes. In pursuit of an answer, we sought to answer the questions below. However, due to various constraints, these aims are still ongoing.

1. Can we get a better estimation of the completeness of our genome assemblies by calculating the number of copies of each repetitive element?
2. What are the different repeats in the draft genome assemblies of the sea cucumber and the brittle star?
3. Can we apply our novel algorithm to estimate the copy number of each repeat on the bases of expected coverage in relation to the coverage of single copy genes?
4. What are the most prevalent repeats in the draft genome assemblies of echinoderms?
5. Are the most prevalent repeats also the same repeats that are differentially expressed in the brittle star during arm regeneration under different conditions?

Materials and Methods

Creating an Assembly of the *A. rubens* Genome

Assembled genomic data for *A. rubens* was collected from GenomeArk hosted by the Vertebrate Genome Project [28]. From this assembly, the bioinformatic programs REPdenovo [7] and RepeatModeler [25] were used to build a library of repetitive genomic elements. RepeatMasker [26] was used to mask the repetitive elements present in the *A. rubens* genome. The results of RepeatMasker were compiled into a more reliable table, and taxonomy was added to the output General Feature Format version 3 (GFF3) file [23]. BUSCO v3 or higher [24] was used to evaluate the quality of the assembly of the genome. The data were then divided up into the 22 longest scaffolds which was used as the *A. rubens* chromosome. The CovEst [12] and GenomeScope [29] programs were also used to estimate the genome size of *A. rubens*. From here, statistics concerning the repetitive elements will be obtained.

Construction of an Improved Classification System for Repetitive Elements

A widespread bibliographical review was conducted on available information concerning the classification of repetitive elements. One specific system devised by Wicker *et al.* [31] was used as a baseline from which to propose adjustments. Our team's goal with this system was to build upon a system of classification that was already being used in the literature but did not accommodate a large variety of repetitive elements. As such, we improved upon this already-published system to allow for a more efficient and accurate categorization and comparison of repetitive elements. Wicker *et al.*'s system has some advantages to the classification of repetitive elements, such as utilizing some terminology currently used in biological classification. For example, the authors use Order, Superfamily, Family, and Subfamily to categorize the various types of repetitive elements.

The current classification system falls short in other ways, however. As in biological classification, the biological meaning of a Genus or species of organism is not attached to its hierarchical level. With the current system of repetitive classification, the levels "Insertion" and "Structural Description," for example, confer biological meaning to the specific repetitive element and are ultimately not meaningful for researchers in classification terms. The current classification system also focuses on solely classifying DNA transposons and Retrotransposons. Past research as implicated numerous types of repetitive genomic elements [32], and we aimed to produce a classification system that can encompass all repetitive elements. Rather than create a system that is completely novel, we opted to build upon the Linnean-style system of classification that is already being used in the literature. These improvements make an easier transition to a more inclusive and organized classification system for repetitive elements.

Analysis of Repetitive Elements in Non-Model Echinoderm Genomes

RNA-seq data for the two non-model echinoderm species, *S. briareus* and *O. brevispinum*, was collected through the the extraction of RNA at three time-points of tissue regeneration (early post-injury phase, growth phase, and differentiation phase). We are in the process of using this data to estimate the number of copies of each repetitive element in the *de novo* assemblies.

Figure 5: Step-by-step procedures for estimating repeat copy numbers based on expected coverage.

First, a *de novo* assembly of repetitive sequences in the genomes of the brittle star and the sea cucumber were built with REPdenovo [7]. An *ab initio* [25] and homology-based [27] technique were then used to predict all repetitive sequences in the echinoderm genomes. Single-copy genes were also identified using BUSCO v3 or higher [24]. Raw reads obtained using REPdenovo were mapped to repeats and exons of single copy genes using tools such as Bowtie2 [19]. The coverage of single copy genes and repetitive elements was then calculated using SAMtools [15] or other related methodologies. The proposed pipeline for the estimation of the number of repetitive elements in the target genomes is outlined in Figure 5. This portion of the research is also currently ongoing.

Results

Improved Classification System for Repetitive Elements

The classification system for repetitive elements devised throughout this research is demonstrated in Table 1 with repeats from the genome of *A. rubens*. More examples of this system, as well as descriptions of terminology, are included in the Appendix. Our classification system improves the current system in the following ways.

1. The classification system of repetitive elements mirrors biological classification by detaching the biological meaning of a Genus or species of organism from its hierarchical classification level. The current system of repetitive sequence classification utilizes the levels "Insertion" and "Structural Description," for example, that confer biological meaning to the specific repetitive element. Our system works to detach this biological meaning of a group of repeats from its hierarchical level by replacing "Insertion" and "Structural Description" with "Type" and "Subtype," respectively.
2. The current system solely classifies DNA transposons and Retrotransposons with no mention of non-transposons, such as repetitive RNA. Our improved system includes a new upper level, Phylum, that divides transposons and non-transposons. As biological classification is used among a wide variety of species, so too is our classification system among a wide variety of repetitive elements.
3. Wicker *et al* classifies LINEs as Orders and Non-LTR retrotransposons as Subclasses. However, we propose that Non-LTR retrotransposons be classified as Orders and LINEs classified as a Family. This is more intuitive, as Wicker *et al* classifies LTR retrotransposons as an Order, not a Subclass of repetitive elements [31].
4. The classification for "Class" has been altered to increase clarity and simplicity. Class 1 elements refer to DNA transposons. Class 2 elements refer to retrotransposons. If a repetitive element is neither, such as repetitive RNA, the classification is simply N/A.
5. Each label after "Order" should be italicized, keeping in accordance with current biological classification systems.
6. The "lead" label, such as Order, *Family*, and *Type*, should be used first for classification. As in established biological classification, categories such as "*Superfamily*" and "*Subfamily*" are not required.
7. The classification "Unknown" is used when more specific labels have been determined but preceding levels of classification have not. [31].

Table 1: Examples of repetitive elements in the *Asterias rubens* genome organized according to the improved classification system proposed herein.

Phylum	Class	Subclass	Order	Superfamily	Family	Subfamily	Type	Subtype
Transposons	1	N/A	Non-LTR retrotransposon	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>SINEs</i>	?	?	?
Transposons	1	N/A	Non-LTR retrotransposon	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>SINEs</i>	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>ALUs</i>	?
Transposons	1	N/A	Non-LTR retrotransposon	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>SINEs</i>	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>MIRs</i>	<i>MIR_Testu</i>
Transposons	1	N/A	Non-LTR retrotransposon	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>LINEs</i>	?	?	?
Transposons	1	N/A	Non-LTR retrotransposon	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>LINEs</i>	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>LINE1</i>	?
Transposons	1	N/A	Non-LTR retrotransposon	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>LINEs</i>	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>LINE2</i>	?
Transposons	1	N/A	Non-LTR retrotransposon	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>LINEs</i>	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>L3/CR1</i>	?
Transposons	1	?	?	?	?	?	?	?
Transposons	1	N/A	LTR retrotransposon	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>ERVL</i>	?
Transposons	1	N/A	LTR retrotransposon	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>ERVL-MaLRs</i>	?
Transposons	1	N/A	LTR retrotransposon	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>ERV_classI</i>	?
Transposons	1	N/A	LTR retrotransposon	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>ERV_classII</i>	?
Transposons	2	?	?	?	?	?	?	?
Transposons	2	1	TIR	<i>hAT</i>	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>hAT-Charlie</i>	?
Transposons	2	1	TIR	<i>Tc1-Mariner</i>	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>TcMar-Tigger</i>	?
Unknown	?	?	?	?	?	?	?	?
Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Interspersed repeats	?	?	?	?	?
Non-transposons	Small RNAs	?	?	?	?	?	?	?
Non-transposons	Simple repeats	Unknown	Satellites	?	?	?	?	?
Non-transposons	Simple repeats	?	?	?	?	?	?	?
Non-transposons	LCRs	?	?	?	?	?	?	?

The use of this classification system should be extended to programs that output annotated repetitive sequences, such as RepeatMasker [26], to further streamline the annotation process. Tables 2, 3, and 4 represent the differences in classification according to RepeatMasker, Wicker *et al* [31], and our improved classification system, respectively. All three tables contain additional examples of repeats from the *A. rubens* genome that have not yet been discussed. The classification of the same randomly-selected DNA sequences from the annotated *A. rubens* genome are compared below.

Table 2: Randomly-selected examples of repetitive elements in the *Asterias rubens* genome organized according to RepeatMasker. Note the limited classification given to these elements in RepeatMasker. Contrast this result with a more extensive and informative classification system conveyed in Tables 3 and 4.

Sequence ID	Start position (bp)	End position (bp)	Classification
scaffold_109_arrow_ctg1	142549	142994	LINE/Dong-R4
scaffold_109_arrow_ctg1	143037	143127	Unknown
scaffold_109_arrow_ctg1	143318	143456	LINE/L2
scaffold_109_arrow_ctg1	143503	143664	Unknown
scaffold_109_arrow_ctg1	144701	144821	LINE/L2
scaffold_109_arrow_ctg1	145512	145572	Unknown
scaffold_109_arrow_ctg1	146155	146372	LINE/L1-Tx1
scaffold_109_arrow_ctg1	146298	146390	Unknown
scaffold_109_arrow_ctg1	146539	146658	Simple_repeat
scaffold_109_arrow_ctg1	147502	147527	Simple_repeat
scaffold_109_arrow_ctg1	153185	153307	LINE/L2
scaffold_109_arrow_ctg1	153360	153416	Unknown
scaffold_109_arrow_ctg1	153461	153791	Unknown
scaffold_109_arrow_ctg1	154944	154992	Simple_repeat
scaffold_109_arrow_ctg1	158553	158594	Simple_repeat
scaffold_109_arrow_ctg1	158691	158728	Simple_repeat
scaffold_109_arrow_ctg1	185372	185422	LTR/Gypsy

Table 3: Randomly-selected examples of repetitive elements in the *Asterias rubens* genome organized according to [31]. Note the more extensive classification that is provided when compared with RepeatMasker. Also note the lack of non-transposons in the table due to the lack of capacity to classify them alongside their transposon counterparts. Refer to our other improvements to this system in the Results above. While reviewing these differences, contrast this classification scheme with an even more extensive and informative classification system conveyed in Table 4.

Sequence ID	Start (bp)	End (bp)	Class	Sub-class	Order	Super-family	Family	Sub-family	Insertion	Structural Description
scaffold_109_arrow_ctg1	142549	142994	Retro-transposons	N/A	LINEs	Unknown	Unknown	Not defined	?	-
scaffold_109_arrow_ctg1	143037	143127	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Not defined	?	-
scaffold_109_arrow_ctg1	143318	143456	Retro-transposons	N/A	LINEs	Unknown	Unknown	Not defined	?	LINE2
scaffold_109_arrow_ctg1	143503	143664	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Not defined	?	-
scaffold_109_arrow_ctg1	144701	144821	Retro-transposons	N/A	LINEs	Unknown	Unknown	Not defined	?	LINE 2
scaffold_109_arrow_ctg1	145512	145572	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Not defined	?	-
scaffold_109_arrow_ctg1	146155	146372	Retro-transposons	N/A	LINEs	Unknown	Unknown	Not defined	?	LINE1
scaffold_109_arrow_ctg1	146298	146390	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Not defined	?	-
scaffold_109_arrow_ctg1	153185	153307	Retro-transposons	N/A	LINEs	Unknown	Unknown	Not defined	?	LINE2
scaffold_109_arrow_ctg1	153360	153416	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Not defined	?	-
scaffold_109_arrow_ctg1	153461	153791	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Not defined	?	-
scaffold_109_arrow_ctg1	185372	185422	Retro-transposons	N/A	LTR retrotransposon	Unknown	Unknown	Not defined	?	-

Table 4: Randomly-selected examples of repetitive elements in the *Asterias rubens* genome organized according to the improved classification system proposed herein. Note this system is the most extensive classification that is provided when compared with [26] and [31]. Also note the presence of non-transposons in the table due to the addition of "Phylum." This allows for these elements to be classified alongside their transposon counterparts. Refer to what other improvements are included in this system that are discussed in the Results above. While reviewing these differences, contrast this classification scheme with the less informative classification schemes in Tables 2 and 3

Sequence ID	Start	End	Phylum	Class	Sub-class	Order	Super-family	Family	Sub-family	Type	Sub-type
scaffold_109 _arrow_ctg1	142549	142994	Transposons	1	N/A	Non-LTR retrotransposons	Unknown	LINEs	?	?	?
scaffold_109 _arrow_ctg1	143037	143127	Unknown	?	?	?	?	?	?	?	?
scaffold_109 _arrow_ctg1	143318	143456	Transposons	1	N/A	Non-LTR retrotransposons	Unknown	LINEs	Unknown	LINE2	?
scaffold_109 _arrow_ctg1	143503	143664	Unknown	?	?	?	?	?	?	?	?
scaffold_109 _arrow_ctg1	144701	144821	Transposons	1	N/A	Non-LTR retrotransposons	Unknown	LINEs	Unknown	LINE2	?
scaffold_109 _arrow_ctg1	145512	145572	Unknown	?	?	?	?	?	?	?	?
scaffold_109 _arrow_ctg1	146155	146372	Transposons	1	N/A	Non-LTR retrotransposons	Unknown	LINEs	Unknown	LINE1	?
scaffold_109 _arrow_ctg1	146298	146390	Unknown	?	?	?	?	?	?	?	?
scaffold_109 _arrow_ctg1	146539	146658	Transposons	Simple repeats	?	?	?	?	?	?	?
scaffold_109 _arrow_ctg1	147502	147527	Transposons	Simple repeats	?	?	?	?	?	?	?
scaffold_109 _arrow_ctg1	153185	153307	Transposons	1	N/A	Non-LTR retrotransposons	Unknown	LINEs	Unknown	LINE2	?
scaffold_109 _arrow_ctg1	153360	153416	Unknown	?	?	?	?	?	?	?	?
scaffold_109 _arrow_ctg1	153461	153791	Unknown	?	?	?	?	?	?	?	?
scaffold_109 _arrow_ctg1	154944	154992	Transposons	Simple repeats	?	?	?	?	?	?	?
scaffold_109 _arrow_ctg1	158553	158594	Transposons	Simple repeats	?	?	?	?	?	?	?
scaffold_109 _arrow_ctg1	158691	158728	Transposons	Simple repeats	?	?	?	?	?	?	?
scaffold_109 _arrow_ctg1	185372	185422	Transposons	1	?	LTR retrotransposons	?	?	?	?	?

Statistics from Non-Model Echinoderm Genomes

The goals below embody the results that were anticipated to support this thesis; however, these aims are still ongoing.

1. By counting the number of repetitive elements, we can achieve a more accurate estimation of the total amount of the genome that has been assembled using a *de novo* approach. This will have applications to all *de novo* assemblies of non-model organisms.
2. By categorizing and quantifying the repeats in echinoderm genomes, we may be able to tell which repetitive elements contribute more to genome size differences among these animals. This may have implications to our understanding of echinoderm genome evolution.
3. Our discovery of the most prevalent type of repetitive elements may also aid in determining the molecular mechanisms by which these elements influence echinoderm tissue regeneration.

Discussion

Effects of an Improved Classification System for Repetitive Elements on Future Research

Our work on the classification of repetitive elements is especially important due to the scientific community's fairly recent realization that repetitive sequences are not so-called "junk DNA" and may serve many functions in biological mechanisms [22, 14, 3]. Many research articles implicating repetitive elements in biological processes, such as tissue regeneration, have been cited above. The classification system that we have proposed was built upon the work by Wicker *et al.* [31]. Widespread bibliographical review aided in combining much of the current consensus surrounding the classification of repetitive elements for integration with Wicker *et al.*'s system. After conducting such a review, our team worked to devise a universal system that made multiple improvements to the current classification scheme.

Our classification system of repetitive elements ultimately detaches the biological meaning of a group of repeats from its hierarchical level through the incorporation of "Phylum," "Type," and "Subtype" categories into the classification system. It goes another step further by also being capable of organizing all types of repetitive elements (transposons or not) into a comparable hierarchical structure. Just as classification is used extensively today in the biological sciences to describe the natural world, so too should this classification system extend to the scientific community's understanding of repetitive elements. Our hope is that the improved classification system will aid in this understanding of repetitive elements, not only for our lab and the experiments we conduct, but for the scientific community as a whole. Our system is another step toward a more universal and coherent classification system for all biological phenomena, including repetitive elements.

Going forward, our knowledge of repetitive elements will certainly improve. As the scientific community discovers unique sequences in the genome, our classification system will help to identify these sequences and their phylogeny to conduct experiments such as the one our lab is currently focusing on. Our understanding of the evolution of repetitive elements may lead us to a molecular explanation for why humans, among most other Chordates, lost their regenerative abilities throughout history. Our increased knowledge of repetitive elements may also lead to the improvement of this classification system. Overall, this system provides an improved framework in which to understand repetitive elements as we know them today as well as provides a foundation for another system in the future.

Impacts of Increased Insight into Repetitive Elements in Non-Model Echinoderm Genomes

The data produced concerning this portion of the team's research will add to the final annotated genomes of the non-model echinoderm species, *Sclerodactyla briareus* and *Ophioderma brevispinum*. These genomic resources will then be submitted to the NCBI's Genbank for use as a powerful source of data in future studies concerning basic and translational research in regenerative biology [2]. The data will also aid postdoctoral student Dr. Janice Kofsky, as well as Dr. Vladimir Mashanov at the Wake Forest University Institute for Regenerative Medicine, in further developing an experimental protocol to modulate gene expression in these adult echinoderm species. The annotated genomes of the sea cucumber and the brittle star will be utilized to conduct these experiments to discover the gene regulatory mechanisms involved in tissue regeneration. Final results obtained from these experiments will yield the fully-annotated genomes of both *Sclerodactyla briareus* and *Ophioderma brevispinum*. The result will also yield insights that demonstrate the importance, or lack thereof, of repetitive elements on gene regulatory networks involved in echinoderm tissue regeneration. If it is confirmed that repetitive elements play a role in the gene regulatory networks surrounding tissue regeneration, future experiments could be conducted with the data to potentially modulate gene expression in other animals and to produce the same regenerative effects observed in echinoderms.

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References

- [1] R. Bannister, I. M. McGonnell, A. Graham, M. C. Thorndyke, and P. W. Beesley. Afuni, a novel transforming growth factor- β gene is involved in arm regeneration by the brittle star *Amphiura filiformis*. *Development Genes and Evolution*, 215(8):393–401, 2005. doi: 10.1007/s00427-005-0487-8.
- [2] D. A. Benson, I. Karsch-Mizrachi, D. J. Lipman, J. Ostell, and D. L. Wheeler. Genbank. *Nucleic Acids Research*, 33(suppl_1):D34–D38, 2005.
- [3] C. R. Boland. Non-coding rna: it’s not junk, 2017.
- [4] G. C. Budd. *Asterias rubens*: common starfish. In T.-W. H. and H. K., editors, *Marine Life Information Network: Biology and Sensitivity Key Information Reviews*. Plymouth: Marine Biological Association of the United Kingdom, 2008.
- [5] R. A. Cameron, P. Kudtarkar, S. M. Gordon, K. C. Worley, and R. . Gibbs. Do echinoderm genomes measure up? *Marine Genomics*, 22:1–9, 2015. doi: 10.1016/j.margen.2015.02.004.
- [6] M. D. C. Carnevali. Regeneration in echinoderms: repair, regrowth, cloning. *Invertebrate Survival Journal*, 3, 2006. URL <http://isj-new.dmz-ext.unimore.it/index.php/ISJ/article/view/124>.
- [7] C. Chu, R. Nielsen, and Y. Wu. REP *denovo*: inferring *de novo* repeat motifs from short sequence reads. *PLOS ONE*, 11(3):1–17, 2016. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0150719.
- [8] S. Dupont and M. Thorndyke. Bridging the regeneration gap: insights from echinoderm models. *Nature Reviews Genetics*, 8, 2007.
- [9] S. I. S. Grewal and S. Jia. Heterochromatin revisited. *Nature Reviews Genetics*, 8(1): 35–46, 2007. doi: 10.1038/nrg2008.
- [10] G. Hendler. *Sea stars, sea urchins, and allies: echinoderms of Florida and the Caribbean*. Smithsonian Institution Press, 1995. ISBN 9781560984504.
- [11] L. A. Hernández-Herrejón, F. A. Solís-Marín, and A. Laguarda-Figueras. Ofiuroideos (echinodermata: Ophiuroidea) de las aguas mexicanas del golfo de méxico. *Revista de Biología Tropical*, 56(3):83–167, 2008.
- [12] M. Hozza, T. Vinař, and B. Brejová. How big is that genome? Estimating genome size and coverage from *k*-mer abundance spectra. In *International Symposium on String Processing and Information Retrieval*, pages 199–209. Springer, 2015.

- [13] E. V. Koonin and M. Galperin. *Sequence—evolution—function: computational approaches in comparative genomics*. Springer Science & Business Media, 2013. ISBN 978-1-4419-5321-6. doi: 10.1007/978-1-4757-3783-7.
- [14] H. Lee, Z. Zhang, and H. M. Krause. Long noncoding rnas and repetitive elements: Junk or intimate evolutionary partners? *Trends in Genetics*, 2019.
- [15] H. Li, B. Handsaker, A. Wysoker, T. Fennell, J. Ruan, N. Homer, G. Marth, G. Abecasis, R. Durbin, and . G. P. D. P. Subgroup. The Sequence Alignment/Map format and SAMtools. *Bioinformatics*, 25(16):2078–2079, 2009. doi: 10.1093/bioinformatics/btp352.
- [16] V. Mashanov, J. Akiona, M. Khoury, J. Ferrier, R. Reid, D. J. Machado, O. Zueva, and D. Janies. Active Notch signaling is required for arm regeneration in a brittle star. *bioRxiv*, 2019. doi: \10.1101/2019.12.13.875401.
- [17] V. S. Mashanov, O. R. Zueva, and J. E. García-Arrarás. Posttraumatic regeneration involves differential expression of long terminal repeat (LTR) retrotransposons. *Developmental Dynamics*, 241(10):1625–1636, 2012. doi: 10.1002/dvdy.23844.
- [18] V. S. Mashanov, O. Zueva, and J. E. García-Arrarás. Postembryonic organogenesis of the digestive tube: why does it occur in worms and sea cucumbers but fail in humans? In *Current Topics in Developmental Biology*, volume 108, pages 185–216. Elsevier, 2014.
- [19] C. Misale. Accelerating bowtie2 with a lock-less concurrency approach and memory affinity. In *2014 22nd Euromicro International Conference on Parallel, Distributed, and Network-Based Processing*, pages 578–585. IEEE, 2014. doi: 10.1109/PDP.2014.50.
- [20] National Center for Biotechnology Information. 25 genomes for 25 years, 2020. URL https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/assembly/GCF_902459465.1.
- [21] G. Nishibuchi and J. Déjardin. The molecular basis of the organization of repetitive dna-containing constitutive heterochromatin in mammals. *Chromosome Research*, 25(1):77–87, 2017. doi: 10.1007/s10577-016-9547-3.
- [22] L. Pray. Transposons, or jumping genes: Not junk DNA. *Nature Education*, 1(1):32, 2008.
- [23] M. G. Reese, B. Moore, C. Batchelor, F. Salas, F. Cunningham, G. T. Marth, L. Stein, P. Flicek, M. Yandell, and K. Eilbeck. A standard variation file format for human genome sequences. *Genome biology*, 11(8):R88, 2010. doi: doi:10.1186/gb-2010-11-8-r88.

- [24] F. A. Simão, R. M. Waterhouse, P. Ioannidis, E. V. Kriventseva, and E. M. Zdobnov. BUSCO: assessing genome assembly and annotation completeness with single-copy orthologs. *Bioinformatics*, 31(19):3210–3212, 2015. doi: 10.1093/bioinformatics/btv351.
- [25] A. F. A. Smit and R. Hubley. RepeatModeler open-1.0. Available from <http://www.repeatmasker.org>, 2008.
- [26] A. F. A. Smit and R. Hubley. RepeatMasker tool. *RepeatModeler Open-1.0.*, 2020.
- [27] M. Tarailo-Graovac and N. Chen. Using RepeatMasker to identify repetitive elements in genomic sequences. *Current Protocols in Bioinformatics*, 25(1):4.10.1–4.10.14, 2009. doi: <https://currentprotocols.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/0471250953.bi0410s25>.
- [28] Vertebrate Genome Project. GenomeArk. *GitHub*, 2020.
- [29] G. W. Vulture, F. J. Sedlazeck, M. Nattestad, C. J. Underwood, H. Fang, J. Gurtowski, and M. C. Schatz. GenomeScope: fast reference-free genome profiling from short reads. *Bioinformatics*, 33(14):2202–2204, 2017.
- [30] Wellcome Sanger Institute. 23 genomes for 25 years, 2017. URL <https://www.sanger.ac.uk/science/collaboration/25-genomes-25-years>.
- [31] T. Wicker, F. Sabot, A. Hua-Van, J. L. Bennetzen, P. Capy, B. Chalhoub, A. Flavell, P. Leroy, M. Morgante, O. Panaud, et al. A unified classification system for eukaryotic transposable elements. *Nature Reviews Genetics*, 8(12):973–982, 2007. doi: 10.1038/nrg2165.
- [32] C. Zhang. Novel functions for small rna molecules. *Current Opinion in Molecular Therapeutics*, 11(6):641, 2009.
- [33] X. Zhang, L. Sun, J. Yuan, Y. Sun, Y. Gao, L. Zhang, S. Li, H. Dai, J.-F. Hamel, C. Liu, et al. The sea cucumber genome provides insights into morphological evolution and visceral regeneration. *PLoS Biology*, 15(10):e2003790, 2017. doi: 10.1371/journal.pbio.2003790.

Appendix

All data, including supplementary digital material described herein, is available at Zenodo (see zenodo.org, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3766936). Other materials will be made available in different manuscripts that are under preparation in Dr. Janies' lab.

A. List of Abbreviations

List of abbreviations used in the improved repeat classification system proposed herein.

- **DIRS**: *Dictyostelium* Intermediate Repeat Sequence
- **ERV**: Endogenous RetroVirus
- **LCR**: Low Complexity Regions
- **LINE**: Long Interspersed Nuclear Elements
- **LTR**: Long Terminal Repeats
- **MER**: ME^Dium Reiterated Repeats
- **MIR**: Mammalian-wide Interspersed Repeats
- **MITE**: Miniature Inverted-repeat Transposable Elements
- **PLE**: Penelope-Like Elements
- **SINE**: Short Interspersed Nuclear Elements
- **SSR**: Simple Sequence Repeats, also known as microsatellites
- **STR**: Short Tandem Repeats
- **TIR**: Terminal Inverted Repeats
- **TNR**: TriNucleotide Repeats

B. Additional Examples

Table 5: Additional examples of repetitive elements that have been organized according to the improved classification system proposed herein.

#	Phylum	Class	Subclass	Order	Superfamily	Family	Subfamily	Type	Subtype
1	Transposons	2	Unknown	Unknown	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>MER1_type</i>	?	?	?
2	Transposons	2	Unknown	Unknown	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>MER2_type</i>	?	?	?
3	Transposons	2	1	TIRs	<i>Tc1-</i> <i>Mariner</i>	<i>Stowaway</i>	<i>Thalos</i>	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>MITEs</i>
4	Transposons	2	1	TIRs	<i>hAT</i>	?	?	?	?
5	Transposons	2	1	TIRs	<i>Mutator</i>	?	?	?	?
6	Transposons	2	1	TIRs	<i>Merlin</i>	?	?	?	?
7	Transposons	2	1	TIRs	<i>Transib</i>	?	?	?	?
8	Transposons	2	1	TIRs	<i>P</i>	?	?	?	?
9	Transposons	2	1	TIRs	<i>PiggyBac</i>	?	?	?	?
10	Transposons	2	1	TIRs	<i>PIF-</i> <i>Harbinger</i>	?	?	?	?
11	Transposons	2	1	TIRs	<i>CACTA</i>	?	?	?	?
12	Transposons	2	1	Crypton	?	?	?	?	?
13	Transposons	2	2	Helitron	?	?	?	?	?
14	Transposons	2	2	Maverick	?	?	?	?	?
15	Transposons	1	N/A	LTR	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>Gypse</i> <i>(mdg4)</i>	?	?	?
16	Transposons	1	N/A	LTR	<i>Copia</i>	<i>Barbara</i>	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>Autonomous retro-transposon</i>
17	Transposons	1	N/A	LTR	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>MER_t_</i> group	?	?	?
18	Transposons	1	N/A	LTR	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>Sukkula</i>	?	?
19	Transposons	1	N/A	LTR	<i>Bel-Pao</i>	?	?	?	?
20	Transposons	1	N/A	LTR	<i>Retrovirus</i>	?	?	?	?
21	Transposons	1	N/A	LTR	<i>ERV</i>	?	?	?	?
22	Transposons	1	N/A	Non-LTR	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>LINEs</i>	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>R2</i>	?
23	Transposons	1	N/A	Non-LTR	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>LINEs</i>	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>RTE</i>	?
24	Transposons	1	N/A	Non-LTR	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>LINEs</i>	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>Jockey</i>	?
25	Transposons	1	N/A	Non-LTR	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>LINEs</i>	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>I</i>	?
26	Transposons	1	N/A	Non-LTR	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>LINEs</i>	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>LINE-</i> <i>1</i>	?
27	Transposons	1	N/A	Non-LTR	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>LINEs</i>	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>LINE-</i> <i>2</i>	?
28	Transposons	1	N/A	Non-LTR	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>SINEs</i>	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>tRNA</i>	?

Table 6: Additional examples of repetitive elements that have been organized according to the improved classification system proposed herein, continued from Table 5.

#	Phylum	Class	Subclass	Order	Superfamily	Family	Subfamily	Type	Subtype
29	Transposons	1	N/A	Non-LTR	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>SINEs</i>	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>7SL</i>	?
30	Transposons	1	N/A	Non-LTR	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>SINEs</i>	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>MIRs</i>	?
31	Transposons	1	N/A	Non-LTR	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>SINEs</i>	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>ALUs</i>	?
32	Transposons	1	N/A	Non-LTR	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>SINEs</i>	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>5S</i>	?
33	Transposons	1	N/A	Non-LTR	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>DIRS</i>	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>Ngaro</i>	?
34	Transposons	1	N/A	Non-LTR	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>DIRS</i>	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>VIPER</i>	?
35	Transposons	1	N/A	Non-LTR	<i>Unknown</i>	<i>PLEs</i>	?	?	?
36	Transposons	1	N/A	Retro- pseudogene	?	?	?	?	?
37	Non- transposons	Simple repeats	N/A	Satellites	<i>N/A</i>	?	?	?	?
38	Non- transposons	Simple repeats	N/A	Satellites	<i>N/A</i>	<i>I</i>	?	?	?
39	Non- transposons	Simple repeats	N/A	Satellites	<i>N/A</i>	<i>II</i>	?	?	?
40	Non- transposons	Simple repeats	N/A	Satellites	<i>N/A</i>	<i>III</i>	?	?	?
41	Non- transposons	Simple repeats	N/A	Satellites	<i>N/A</i>	<i>Alpha</i> satellites	?	?	?
42	Non- transposons	Simple repeats	N/A	Satellites	<i>N/A</i>	<i>Mini-</i> satellites	?	?	?
43	Non- transposons	Simple repeats	N/A	Satellites	<i>N/A</i>	<i>SSRs</i>	?	?	?
44	Non- transposons	STRs	N/A	TNRs	<i>N/A</i>	?	?	?	?
45	Non- transposons	STRs	N/A	Telomeric repeats	<i>N/A</i>	?	?	?	?
46	Non- transposons	STRs	N/A	Subtelomeric repeats	<i>N/A</i>	?	?	?	?
47	Non- transposons	Small RNAs	N/A	micro RNAs	<i>N/A</i>	?	?	?	?

Table 7: Additional examples of repetitive elements that have been organized according to the improved classification system proposed herein, continued from Table 6.

#	Phylum	Class	Subclass	Order	<i>Superfamily</i>	<i>Family</i>	<i>Subfamily</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Subtype</i>
48	Non-transposons	Small RNAs	N/A	small interfering RNAs	<i>N/A</i>	?	?	?	?
49	Non-transposons	Small RNAs	N/A	small interfering RNAs	<i>N/A</i>	<i>piwi-interacting RNAs</i>	?	?	?
50	Non-transposons	Small RNAs	N/A	transfer RNAs	<i>N/A</i>	?	?	?	?
51	Non-transposons	Small RNAs	N/A	small nuclear RNAs	<i>N/A</i>	?	?	?	?
52	Non-transposons	Small RNAs	N/A	ribosomal RNAs	<i>N/A</i>	?	?	?	?
53	Non-transposons	Small RNAs	N/A	double stranded RNAs	<i>N/A</i>	?	?	?	?
54	Non-transposons	LCRs	N/A	?	<i>N/A</i>	?	?	?	?